

A Study of Iron Concretions in Lateritic Soil of West Bengal

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Iron concretions of various sizes are present in lateritic soils of West Bengal. The soils are acidic and free iron oxides are present abundantly. From analysis of the outer iron coating and the inner core of the concretions it appears that these have formed by leaching down of iron and manganese in the reduced state and their deposition in concentric lamination over a nucleus which is either a particle of quartz or parent material. Alternate wet and dry seasons that prevail is an essential condition for formation of these iron concretions.

IN West Bengal lateritic and red soils constitute an important soil group, covering the western part of the State. The soils are red in colour of various shades, variable in depth and iron concretions of various sizes range from thick indurated cemented mass to only a few detached particles. A study of the characteristics of these iron concretions was made to obtain their genesis, the results of which are presented in this paper.

Materials and Methods :

Four representative soil profiles from the lateritic area of West Bengal were selected for the study, all belonging to plinth paleustalf. Their morphological descriptions are given below. Soil colour is under moist condition according to Munsell Colour Chart.

Profile 1.

Situated in village Pacha Dahara, P. S. Bishnupur, Dist. Bankura, very gently sloping upland with normal relief, well drained, *Sal* forest with thorny plants.

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|----|-----------|--|
| A1 | 0-8 cm | Yellowish red (5YR5/6) loam, crumb structure, slightly hard when dry, friable when moist, sticky when wet, some iron concretions, clear and smooth boundary. |
| A2 | 8-15 cm | Yellowish red (5YR4/6) clay loam, crumb structure, hard when dry, firm when moist, sticky when wet, some iron concretions along with quartz particles, clear boundary. |
| B1 | 15-65 cm | Red (2.5YR4/6) clay loam, sub-angular blocky, hard when dry, firm when moist, sticky when wet, many iron concretions, clear and smooth boundary. |
| B2 | 65-100 cm | Red (2.5YR4/6) clay, angular blocky, very hard when dry, very |

firm when moist, very sticky, clay skin on ped faces, many iron concretions, clear boundary.

- | | | |
|---|---------|---|
| C | 100 cm+ | Murram mass along with hard and compact iron concretions with some soil matrix. |
|---|---------|---|

Profile 2.

Situated in village Kuliajan, P. S. Bishnupur, Dist. Bankura, level upland with normal relief, well drained waste land, with occasional bushy shrubs.

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|----|-------------|--|
| A1 | 0-7 cm | Light reddish brown (5YR6/4) sandy loam, crumb structure, loose when dry, friable when moist, nonsticky, few fine roots, clear and smooth boundary. |
| AB | 7-32 cm | Yellowish red (5YR5/4) sandy clay loam, crumb to granular structure, slightly hard when dry, friable when moist, slightly sticky, few fine roots, gradual and smooth boundary. |
| B2 | 32-90 cm | Red (2.5YR5/6) clay loam, angular blocky, slightly hard when dry, friable when moist, slightly sticky, a few iron concretions, evidence of clay skins in patches, gradual and smooth boundary. |
| B3 | 90-130 cm | As above, with many iron concretions and quartz particles. |
| C | 130-150 cm+ | Hard murram mass with iron concretions. |

Profile 3.

Situated in village Piardoba, P. S. Bishnupur, Dist. Bankura, well drained upland with normal relief, very gently sloping. Village forest but with scanty vegetation.

- A1 0-9 cm Yellowish red (5YR4/6) sandy loam, crumb structure, slightly hard when dry, friable when moist, slightly sticky, a few iron concretions, clear and smooth boundary.
- A2 9-39 cm Yellowish red (5YR4/6) loam, sub-angular blocky, slightly hard when dry, friable when moist, slightly sticky, a few iron concretions, clear boundary.
- B1 39-58 cm Red (2.5YR4/6) clay loam, angular blocky structure, friable when moist, sticky when wet, more iron concretions, gradual boundary.
- B2 58-150 cm Red (2.5YR4/6) clay, strong angular blocky, firm when moist, very sticky when wet, many iron concretions, clear boundary.
- C 150 cm+ Murrum mass with many iron concretions and soil matrix.

Profile 4.

Situated in State Soil Conservation Research Farm, Midnapur, well drained level upland, formerly under cultivation, currently fallow.

- A 0-15 cm Yellowish red (5YR5/6) silty loam, sub-angular blocky, hard when dry, friable when moist, sticky when wet, clear and smooth boundary.
- AB 15-75 cm Reddish yellow (5YR6/8) silty clay loam, sub-angular blocky, hard when dry, friable when moist, sticky when wet, a few small iron concretions.
- B2 75-120 cm Strong brown (7.5YR5/8) silty clay loam, angular blocky, hard when dry, firm when moist, sticky when wet, many iron concretions, gradual and smooth boundary.
- B3 120-150 cm Reddish yellow (7.5YR6/6) silty clay loam, angular blocky, hard when dry, firm when moist, more iron concretions, clear boundary.
- C 150 cm+ Weathered parent material along with iron concretions.

In all the areas granite, gneiss and occasionally schists constitute the geological rocks. Natural vegetation consists of *Sal* (*Shorea robusta*), *Palas* (*Butea frondosa*), *Babul* (*Acacia nilotica*), bamboos and grasses.

The climate of the region is characterised by hot summer months April to June, wet monsoon months July to September or October and mild winter months November to February or March. The mean annual rainfall is about 1200 to 1500 mm, about 75% of which is received during the monsoon months, the rest of the year being fairly dry. Only during the four monsoon months precipitation is more than evaporation and wet condition results, but during the rest of the year evaporation is more than precipitation and dry period prevails. There is thus distinct alternate wet and dry seasons in the area and ustic moisture regime prevails.

Standard methods were followed for analysis of the soil and concretion samples (Piper¹, Jackson²).

Results and Discussion

Morphological descriptions of the soils show that the surface horizon has yellowish red to reddish brown colour all with hue 5YR. The red colour persists in lower horizons. The texture is sandy loam to loam and silty loam at the surface which becomes some what heavier in lower layers. Dark coloured or brown, medium hard to hard, round to sub-rounded iron concretions are present in all the profiles. They are generally only a few in number at the surface but become more abundant with depth. Finally at 100 to 150 cm depth in the C horizon there is the compact layer of iron concretions, weathered parent material and soil matrix.

The more important physical and physico-chemical properties of soils are given in Table 1. All the soils are acidic. The acidity decreases with depth. The cation exchange capacity is low, and so is the organic carbon content.

The clay mineral consists dominantly of kaolinite along with some illite.

All the soils contain variable amounts of free iron oxides. Both the oxalate extractable (by method of McKeague and Day³) and dithionite extractable (by method of Alexander⁴) iron oxides, giving the amorphous and the crystalline oxide contents respectively increase with depth, showing their mobility down the profile (Table 2). There is a slight but distinct tendency for the active iron ratio Fe_o/Fe_a to increase down the profile, suggesting that the initial rate of release of iron from primary minerals is relatively rapid in relation to the rate of crystallisation of the secondary iron compounds. Total iron also increases with depth. Manganese content is low, but this also increases slightly in lower horizons.

The iron concretions in these soils are variable in size, being small in the upper horizons, but becoming bigger and more abundant in lower depths. The surface colour of the concretion is reddish yellow to pink and reddish brown, all with

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS

Horizon cm	Mechanical composition %				pH	Organic C (%)	C.E.C. me/100 g	Base saturation (%)
	Coarse sand	Fine sand	Silt	Clay				
<i>Profile 1</i>								
0-8	31.9	29.3	17.6	21.2	5.3	0.086	2.82	22
8-15	32.4	21.9	20.8	24.9	5.5	0.047	3.32	28
15-65	37.0	18.9	13.6	30.5	6.0	0.046	4.32	41
65-100	24.3	14.8	15.6	45.3	6.3	0.043	7.78	61
<i>Profile 2</i>								
0-7	42.9	34.7	8.2	14.2	6.25	0.086	1.58	29
7-32	43.0	27.8	6.5	22.7	4.8	0.065	2.16	18
32-90	33.3	25.9	16.6	24.2	5.6	0.043	3.57	28
90-130	30.9	19.2	20.5	29.4	6.0	0.054	6.04	53
<i>Profile 3</i>								
0-9	50.0	21.0	11.2	17.8	4.8	0.113	1.96	24
9-39	42.2	21.5	14.3	22.0	5.15	0.081	3.07	33
39-58	39.5	21.2	10.8	28.5	4.45	0.054	2.70	34
58-150	40.7	16.0	8.2	35.1	5.75	0.036	4.43	49
<i>Profile 4</i>								
0-15	37.1	20.1	26.2	16.6	5.1	0.130	3.57	37
15-75	25.6	13.6	30.2	30.6	5.05	0.054	5.41	47
75-120	30.8	12.2	25.4	31.6	5.45	0.043	7.40	58
120-150	27.8	12.5	26.9	32.8	5.85	0.011	9.03	65

TABLE 2—IRON AND MANGANESE CONTENTS IN SOILS (%)

Horizon cm	Total iron Fe ₂ O ₃	Oxalate extractable iron (Fe _o)	Dithionite extractable iron (Fe _d)	Fe _o Fe _d	Total MnO
<i>Profile 1</i>					
0-8	5.01	0.76	1.47	0.52	0.02
8-15	8.86	0.82	1.17	0.70	0.03
15-65	10.26	1.52	2.02	0.75	0.06
65-100	10.24	1.03	1.53	0.67	0.09
<i>Profile 2</i>					
0-7	3.81	0.57	0.91	0.63	0.05
7-32	5.21	0.87	1.03	0.84	0.07
32-90	4.39	1.01	1.24	0.81	0.04
90-130	7.52	1.04	1.29	0.81	0.13
<i>Profile 3</i>					
0-9	3.61	0.63	0.89	0.71	0.06
9-39	5.70	0.88	1.21	0.73	0.05
39-58	8.56	1.13	1.49	0.76	0.07
58-150	9.60	1.50	1.75	0.86	0.12
<i>Profile 4</i>					
0-15	5.01	0.98	1.12	0.88	0.06
15-75	7.26	1.37	1.78	0.77	0.07
75-120	9.82	1.06	1.30	0.82	0.05
120-150	9.83	1.43	1.58	0.91	0.12

hue 5YR. On breaking the concretion the inner core was found to have reddish yellow to reddish brown and dark reddish brown colour, sometime with black specks.

The concretion has always a nucleus or central core of quartz or parent material particle or clay aggregate around which there has been deposition of iron and manganese in concentric lamination. This is clear from examination of a broken concretion under a low power microscope. Evidently, the concretion has gradually grown in size by deposition of iron and manganese oxides.

For convenience of study, the concretions were separated into two groups according to their size, namely (i) those with diameter between 2 and 5 mm and (ii) those with more than 5 mm diameter. In this study, very small concretions of less than 2 mm size were not included.

The chemical compositions of the outer coating and the inner core of the concretion were estimated. For this, concretions from each of the two groups were treated with hot 6N HCl so as to dissolve the outer coating and the extract was analysed for the various constituents. The results are shown in Table 3. The residue or the insoluble part left after acid extraction, may be taken as the nucleus or the core. There is very little difference between the residues from the smaller and the larger size concretions in each horizon.

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TABLE 3—ANALYSIS OF HCl EXTRACT OF CONCRETIONS (% COATING)

Size mm	Insoluble %	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	Mn	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	$\frac{Fe}{Mn}$
<i>Profile 1</i>									
<i>8-15 cm</i>									
2-5	84.6	63.56	16.50	14.90	1.10	0.59	1.62	1.90	3.0
5+	88.6	58.68	13.77	23.33	0.95	0.35	1.56	1.40	1.8
<i>15-65 cm</i>									
2-5	90.8	54.90	12.28	23.91	2.28	1.30	3.80	1.52	1.6
5+	92.8	60.42	15.41	14.17	2.64	1.11	3.75	2.50	3.0
<i>65-100 cm</i>									
2-5	70.2	70.88	15.17	10.43	0.57	0.94	1.57	0.42	4.8
5+	67.6	72.54	13.31	9.98	0.71	0.18	0.95	0.35	5.2
<i>Profile 2</i>									
<i>32-90 cm</i>									
2-5	94.8	59.92	3.65	15.39	3.08	2.31	10.77	4.81	2.6
5+	94.2	63.10	7.41	20.86	1.55	0.70	3.62	2.76	2.1
<i>Profile 3</i>									
<i>9-39 cm</i>									
2-5	95.4	58.86	17.83	9.57	1.52	1.73	5.00	5.43	4.3
5+	95.0	66.60	8.60	16.60	1.20	0.40	2.00	4.60	2.8
<i>39-58 cm</i>									
2-5	94.8	60.00	6.34	15.77	2.70	2.11	6.16	6.90	2.7
5+	94.4	58.40	11.78	18.02	0.89	1.25	4.46	5.18	2.7
<i>58-150 cm</i>									
2-5	93.8	58.68	16.13	13.55	1.77	0.98	4.20	4.51	3.0
5+	94.0	62.23	16.83	9.17	1.83	2.00	3.16	4.82	4.9
<i>Profile 4</i>									
<i>75-120 cm</i>									
2-5	76.8	65.58	10.86	16.77	1.76	1.36	2.28	1.36	2.7
5+	80.0	68.95	11.90	15.00	1.15	0.60	0.95	1.45	3.2

TABLE 4—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF CORE OF CONCRETIONS AFTER HCl TREATMENT

Horizon cm	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	Mn	CaO	MgO	K ₂ O	$\frac{SiO_2}{R_2O_3}$
<i>Profile 1</i>								
<i>8-15</i>								
15-65	89.86	6.23	3.24	Tr	0.35	0.14	0.18	18.5
65-100	87.80	7.32	4.32	Tr	0.28	0.12	0.16	14.9
	87.90	1.34	10.24	0.78	0.42	0.27	0.05	19.6
<i>Profile 2</i>								
<i>32-90</i>								
	94.97	2.43	2.04	Tr	0.26	0.24	0.06	42.8
<i>Profile 3</i>								
<i>9-39</i>								
39-58	90.92	6.17	2.40	Tr	0.12	0.16	0.23	20.0
58-150	91.68	4.36	3.32	Tr	0.23	0.25	0.16	23.9
	95.17	2.05	2.08	Tr	0.39	0.22	0.11	48.1
<i>Profile 4</i>								
<i>75-120</i>								
	91.01	2.58	5.68	0.12	0.38	0.15	0.08	24.9

In the HCl extract the total sesquioxides vary but Fe_2O_3 is always present in larger amount. There is a general trend that at lower depth of the soil more iron and manganese have deposited as concretion which are extractable by acid. Fe/Mn ratio is variable and so the proportions of iron and manganese are not related to the size of the core. Leaching down of the elements through the soil profile to form the concretion has not been uniform. TiO_2 content is extremely low. Other basic oxides are also very low and so these have no participation in the formation of the concretion.

The residue left after acid extraction was also analysed after crushing and fusion with sodium carbonate. In this case the residue of both the size groups were mixed and composite samples were made. The analytical data are presented in Table 4. In all cases the residue after acid extraction was white in colour on the outer surface.

It may be concluded that the core over which the concretion has formed is made up largely of quartz particle or may be a particle of the parent material.

Conclusion: Depending upon the characteristics of the iron concretions classification have sometimes been suggested by some workers. Pawluk and Dumanski⁵, working on a poorly drained soil of Alberta found the concretions localised in the zones of strongest mottling and were more abundantly distributed in A than in B horizon.

Iron concretions in the lateritic soil of West Bengal under study are irreversibly hard particles, rounded to sub-rounded in shape, the size increasing with depth.

In the formation of the soil abundant rainfall, but with alternate wet and dry conditions and oxidising and reducing changes under free internal drainage have resulted in leaching down of iron by solubilisation by its reduction into ferrous state and its subsequent precipitation in the ferric form in the lower part of the soil profile. A nucleus for such deposition in lamination or concentric form is essential which is either a quartz or a parent rock particle. Manganese also moves along with iron for formation of the concretion. The rates of movement of iron and manganese are, however, variable, as has already been discussed. There are several conditions favourable for deposition of iron and manganese by arrestment of their downward movement and oxidation. These are changes in soil pH, change in redox potential, dry oxidising state or also may be the fluctuation of ground water level. It, however, needs to be stressed that the essential condition for formation of the concretions is that the soil profile must be saturated with water at some season. Alternate wetting and drying as occurs in the lateritic area have resulted in their irreversible hardening.

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